

Qualitative Study on Belief and Attitude of Secondary School Students on Effective Teaching and Learning of Mathematics in Nigeria

*Julius, Elizabeth Ph.D.¹

Email: elizabeth.julius@ksusta.edu.ng

Tel: 08030767562

Dantani, Emmanuel¹

Email: gwamirisiking@gmail.com

Tel: 08068705457

¹Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Kebbi State University of Science and Technology Aliero

Abstract

This paper focused on qualitative study on belief and attitude of secondary school students on effective teaching and learning of mathematics in Nigeria. The study employs the method of narrative reviews for the synthesis of findings and emphasizes the importance of the role of attitude and belief toward mathematics, which contributes to achieving high performance in the subject. It was suggested in the study that teachers should always examine their students' attitude and provide appropriate support to stimulate the development of a positive attitude toward the subject. Furthermore, it was recommended among others that researchers should conduct additional studies to identify the factors leading to the development of students' negative attitude toward mathematics. These efforts might help students to develop a positive attitude toward mathematics and therefore achieve a higher performance level in the subject.

Keyword: Student's belief, Student's attitude, Mathematics teaching, Mathematics Learning, Students, Teaching and Learning

Introduction

The competence gain in the study of mathematics is widely used in all spheres of human life. Mathematics plays a key role in shaping how individuals deal with the various spheres of private, social, and civil life (Leal et al. 2022). This justifies the compulsion of the study of the subject by all students who go through basic and secondary education in most countries. Mathematics is therefore a core subject at these levels of education in Nigeria. It is regrettable, therefore, that in the contemporary times many students struggle with mathematics and perform terribly low in their final examinations in most jurisdictions. Students' performance in mathematics at the senior secondary school has not been encouraging. Candidates are reported to exhibit poor understanding of mathematical concepts and are unable to form the appropriate mathematical models which could be tackled with the requisite skills" (Chief Examiner's Report, 2016, 20017, 2018, 2022). It has also been realised that many students have developed negative attitude towards the study of mathematics as a result of mass failure of students of the subject. It is an irrefutable fact that the successfulness of learning the subject is contingent on myriad of factors. School, classroom, student and teacher factors all impinge on the learning of mathematics. In particular, the seriousness or otherwise attached to the teaching of mathematics invariably affects students' performance in their final examinations.

Educational researchers have expended time and energy trying to unravel the possible causes of students' poor attitudes and performance in mathematics. An area that has not been explored extensively is the influence of teacher attitude on student attitude towards the study of the subject. Research findings indicate that effective teachers facilitate learning by truly caring about their students' engagement and creating the right atmosphere that enhances student learning (Fernandez et al., 2020). They have high yet realistic expectations about enhancing students' capacity to think, reason, communicate, reflect upon and critique their own practice, and they provide students with opportunities to ask why the class is doing certain things and with what effect (Watson, 2021). The relationships develop in the classroom become a resource for developing students' attitudes and mathematical competencies and identities. These resources are very essential to the learning of mathematics.

Attitude as a concept is concerned with an individual's way of thinking, acting and behaving. It has very serious implications for the learner, the teacher, the immediate social group with which the individual learner relates, and the entire school system. Attitudes are formed as a result of some kind of learning experiences students go through. This is mimicry, which also has a part to play in the teaching and learning situation. In this respect, the learner draws from his teachers' disposition to form his own belief and attitude, which may likely affect his learning outcomes (Malvasi & Gil-Quintana 2022).

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Learning mathematics does not only involve thinking and reasoning, it is dependent on the attitudes of the learners towards learning mathematics. Han and Carpenter (2014) state that attitudes consist of cognitive, affective and behavioural reactions that individuals display towards an object or the surrounding based on their feelings or interest. The cognitive component of attitude is what the individual thinks or believes about mathematics. The affective component of attitude is the feeling or emotions of the individual associated with learning mathematics (Ingram, 2015). Thus, the affective component is the source of driving the engagement of students towards mathematics. Furthermore, the affective aspect is also influenced by the belief formed from the cognitive component of attitude, which creates a mindset that becomes constant overtime and influences the feelings of the students towards learning mathematics (Ingram, 2015; Zan & Di Martino, 2010). As such, the cognitive and affective components of attitude are interrelated and deeply interact with each other.

The behavioural aspect of attitude is the tendency to respond in a certain way towards learning mathematics. Behavioural attitude is also influenced by affective attitude. Student feeling confident in doing mathematics is linked with being successful in mathematics, which is regarded as a positive behaviour. If students are not confident in doing mathematics, they may not experience success, and unsuccessful behaviour is regarded as negative feelings (Zan & Di Martino, 2017). Hence the behavioural component of attitude impacts on the cognitive component of attitude as well. When students see the importance of mathematics in real lives, they feel engaged, confident and connected to their learning. As such, the three components of attitude, confidence, awareness on the importance of mathematics and engagement are interrelated (Mensah et al., 2013).

An important question that arises here is how can an increased level of confidence, awareness on the importance of mathematics and engagement be achieved so that students' attitudes towards learning mathematics become more positive? Teaching mathematics in a meaningful context could be the solution. Setting mathematical problems in a context can help students see the application of mathematics (Ministry of Education, 2020). In mathematics education, a range of meanings exists for the term context. According to Hidayatullah & Csikos, (2023), a context is an event that takes place in a set environment. The learning environment is the situation context and the characteristics of the task make up the task context.

Boyd and Hipkins (2015) confirmed in their report, which was based on Sport in Education Programme, that students feel more engaged and confident being taught in a sporting context. Students who were part are reported to have an increased sense of belonging and pride in their school. Afari et al., (2013) investigated the impact of using mathematical games on college students' attitudes towards learning Mathematics. A pre-post design method was used to assess students' perception of the learning environment and their attitude towards learning Mathematics. Eight classes out of 33 used a games context. The students from the classes that used games found their lessons more interactive, got involved and enjoyed learning Mathematics. Rarujanai et al., (2022) stated that games and sports are the best way to build students' engagement and confidence in mathematics. There are a number of advantages of using a sporting context to teach mathematics as most students can relate to sports and can understand the rules and meanings that are presented to them. Students enjoy sports and show a greater level of interest when sports is applied to mathematics. Yuanita & Zulnaidi (2018) argues that mathematics is the science of space, number, quantity and arrangement and these four elements feature in every sport, making it the most relevant context in which mathematics can be taught.

Attard (2012); Grootenboer et al., (2008); Mata et al. (2012), have identified important factors that contribute to students' attitudes towards learning mathematics, these include the students themselves, the school, the teachers' beliefs and attitudes and their teaching methods. The teachers' teaching methods have a major influence on students' attitudes. Teachers can do many things to facilitate the classroom learning to alleviate students' engagement level and confidence in learning mathematics (Attard, 2012; Kele & Sharma, 2014). According to Sullivan and McDonough (2007), teachers can find ways to encourage student engagement and confidence in learning mathematics. This can be achieved by implementing meaningful activities embedded in real-life contexts.

Learning mathematics has become a necessity for an individual's full development in today's complex society. Despite its utility and importance, mathematics is perceived by most pupils as difficult, boring, not very practical, and abstract, etc (Ignacio, Nieto & Barona, 2006). Therefore, students' low success level in mathematics has been a worry for a long time in many countries and Nigeria in particular. There are a lot of factors affecting students' success in mathematics. One of these factors is their mathematical attitude of fears (Peker & Mirasyedioglu, 2008). One of the reasons for mathematical fears is attitude towards mathematics (Baloglu, 2001). It is generally believed that students' attitudes towards mathematics determine their mathematical success. A student's constant failure in mathematics and his/her mathematics anxiety can make him to believe that he can never do well on the subject thus accepting defeat. On the other hand, his successful experience can make him develop a positive attitude towards learning mathematics. So, the importance of measuring students' attitudes increases every passing day into educational system (Gerçek et al. 2006). In a teaching setting in which student's attitudes are not considered,

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expected learning experiences become difficult and hence teaching activities are not precisely performed. Whereas, conducting teaching activities are the signs for students' success in education. To achieve the expected student success, it is required to understand students' attitude because one of the objectives of elementary mathematics education is to get student improve affirmative attitudes towards mathematics (Vosniadou, et al. 2020).

Determining how much students reached the educational objectives will be beneficial for assessing of the current education and, determining student attitudes which can be affected by different variables beneficial for remediation of students' disregard, biases and learning difficulties about mathematics (Vosniadou, et al. 2020) Considering education as a process which is deliberate, has goals and aims to have students gain a positive behavioral change through this process, it is hoped that attitudes of students towards mathematics positively improves through this process in all levels of elementary schools. Students' attitudes towards mathematics changes according to some variables such as gender, whether receives private tuition, mathematics achievement score, educational background of parents, profession of parents and grade levels etc.

The terms 'conceptions' and 'beliefs' are used interchangeably, as conceptions and beliefs are not directly observable and have to be inferred, therefore, it is problematic to have a common definition of these notions. Nevertheless, educationalists have tried to define these terms in a variety of ways. For instance, Sangcap, (2010) defines 'beliefs' as personal principles, constructed from experience that an individual employ, often unconsciously, to interpret new experiences and information and to guide action. Saadati et al., (2019) refers to 'conceptions' as conscious or subconscious beliefs, understanding, meaning, mental images, and preferences. Based on these definitions, the working definition of these terms for the study is that 'conceptions are conscious and unconscious cognitive and affective beliefs, personal meaning, mental images and preferences constructed from experiences within and beyond schooling.

Mathematics is at the heart of many successful careers and successful lives for societal development, particularly in the extraordinary and accelerating change circumstances. However, in reality, most people in general and students in particular dislike mathematics. The review of school-based educational research has revealed that the majority of secondary school students find mathematics as the most difficult, abstract, tedious, deadly, and boring subject (Prendergast et al., 2018). Moreover, study found that students in primary schools enjoy Mathematics but when they move to secondary school their interest towards the subject declines (Perera & John, 2020). The negative conceptions or beliefs about mathematics have a major impact on students' achievement, enrollment in higher education and their future career decisions.

Generally, students' views of mathematics are developed based on their school learning experiences and how the public image of mathematics is portrayed in the society. To elaborate, in general it is believed that males are born with innate capabilities of making sense of abstract ideas and as mathematics is also an abstract level subject boy can do well as compared to girls (Iannone & Simpson, 2019). Some of the other viewpoints' students hold about mathematics include: mathematics problems have one and only one answer and they can be solved in a particular way; mathematics is a solitary activity, done by individuals in isolation; mathematics requires good memory and is only for clever ones (Iannone & Simpson, 2019).

People's incorrect beliefs about and negative attitudes towards mathematics have had a devastating impact on the teaching and learning of mathematics in our culture. Intense negative emotions around mathematics are not uncommon and are recognised as 'mathematics trauma' or 'mathematics anxiety'. Mathematics, more than any other subject, has the power to crush students' spirits, and many adults do not move on from mathematics experiences in school if they are negative (Boaler, 2016). Taking a cultural perspective of mathematics will engage students' imagination and creativity and provide students with a strong understanding of what mathematics is and why we do it. Connecting culture and mathematics will allow indigenous students to learn mathematics from their own cultural knowledge and first language (Matthews, 2015). Changing learners' experience of mathematics is not as simple as changing the nature of the mathematical tasks that teachers set: 'For change to be successful, teachers' beliefs, attitudes and practices need to be aligned' (Ontario Principals' Council, 2019).

Stipek and colleagues found that teachers who didn't enjoy or feel confident about teaching mathematics were also those who articulated very traditional beliefs about mathematics. However, teachers who were more positive and confident about teaching mathematics expressed beliefs that were more reform-based (Stipek et al. 2001). They suggested that increasing teachers' self-confidence in mathematics by building their mathematical understanding could be important in moving teachers towards more inquiry orientated beliefs and practices. This is best achieved by involving teachers in ongoing job-embedded staff development that revolves around mathematics teaching and learning to improve their understanding and confidence (Ontario Principals' Council, 2019).

Recent brain research tells us that everyone with the right experiences, messages and effective teaching can be successful in mathematics at the highest level (Boaler, 2016). Professor Jo Boaler acknowledges that some teachers find this difficult to accept 'especially if they have spent many years deciding who can and who can't do mathematics and teaching them

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accordingly'. This is not saying that everyone's brain is the same; it is saying that brain differences at birth are far less significant than the influence of learning experiences in rich and challenging environments. Therefore, the message struggling learners should tell themselves is not 'I can't do this', but 'I can't do this yet'. This is a really important message because people need to believe in their ability to learn mathematics, mathematicians are made not born. Too often we talk about 'mathematical ability' whereas emphasis is put much more on effort than ability (Churchman, 2015).

The work of Carol Dweck on fixed and growth mind-sets is particularly relevant to the learning of mathematics (Darmawan et al., 2020). Researchers have shown that learners, who develop a growth mind-set, believing that they can develop their intellectual ability through perseverance and effort, have positive attitudes and on-going growth in mathematical achievement (Boaler 2016). On the other hand, those with fixed mind-sets perform poorly across the achievement spectrum, as they believe that talent is something you either have or you don't and, no matter how much effort is expended, it does not change. High achieving girls can be particularly vulnerable if they believe in a fixed mind-set, losing confidence when faced with intellectual challenge, becoming fearful of no longer being seen as smart if they make mistakes. On the other hand, when they recognise that working hard develops skills and ability, it is less likely that their confidence or their performances are undermined (Darmawan et al., 2020).

Neuroscientists Erin Maloney and colleagues found that parents with mathematics anxiety who frequently helped their children with mathematics homework in the early years diminished their children's learning of mathematics (Maloney et al. 2015). Research shows that when parents experience mathematics anxiety, they often hold poor attitudes about mathematics, considering it of little use and expressing low motivation to succeed in mathematics. This in turn demotivates their children, increasing mathematics anxiety and reluctance to embrace challenges. However, if parents' mathematics fears can be reduced, this will lead to more positive homework experiences, and most likely result in improved mathematics achievement and diminished mathematics anxiety for their children.

Brouseau (1997) identified a common expectation in many mathematics classrooms which he termed the 'Didactic Contract'. When students ask for help, they expect their teacher to break down the problem and make it easier, thus diminishing the cognitive demands of the task. Thus, rather than thinking, reasoning and sense making, students consider their role is one of 'paying careful attention' (Boaler, 2016). However, when learners seek relational understanding (knowing what to do and why), ideas make sense and there is an affective as well as a cognitive benefit. This fosters a positive self-concept and gives learners the confidence that they can learn and understand mathematics, diminishing mathematics anxiety. Many Aboriginal students will need encouragement to take risks when learning mathematics, as they are traditionally taught to observe and wait until they are confident, they have mastered a skill (Rinco et al., 2021).

Teaching and learning like any other subject taught in school other than mathematics implies to the act of belief and attitude displayed either by the teacher, student, parents, school authority, etc which will result to positive or negative outcome in teaching and learning. When students constantly fail mathematics subject, even if they have positive expression about the subject their belief system will change thereby accepting any negative impression to the subject and if they already have negative impression on the subject their belief system will be overpowered in failing the subject (Dantani, 2023). The attitude of fear of mathematics by students is one of the major problems for researchers to conduct investigation and answer question of what, why, where, and who? That is, what is the reason for the fear? Why do you fear mathematics? Where is the fear in mathematics begin and who is responsible for the fear of mathematics? Answers to these questions and more others will help in addressing the issue of fear by the students. And also, if students' attitude towards learning mathematics is negative or positive, their belief toward the subject should be questioned whether they consider it as the most difficult, abstract, tedious, deadly and boring subject. The school, the teachers and their teaching methods will serve as a medium of change to student attitude toward the subject (Dantani, 2023). When teachers motivate their students, the attitude student have on mathematics can change automatically. Teachers have a lot to do in helping students to regain their interest toward mathematics learning especially adopting different techniques and strategies, either through games, storytelling, demonstration, music, etc. This will assist them develop positive mindset about the learning of mathematics subject (Dantani, 2023).

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine secondary school students' beliefs and attitudes toward mathematics teaching and learning.

Research Question

What is the belief and attitude of secondary school students toward mathematics teaching and learning?

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Methodology

The method of narrative reviews is selected for the synthesis of finding. Baumeister (2013), states that narrative reviews combine results for several studies that may use different procedures and methods to answer different questions. In this paper, the researcher presents the contributions with the available literature and previous studies to draw its findings. The studies presented how related student's beliefs and attitudes toward mathematics teaching and learning are connected. Therefore, the studies presented are synthesized and used to make conclusions and recommendations of this paper.

Results

This study is a small-scale study for some of the insights into students' conceptions, beliefs and attitudes towards teaching and learning mathematics. Interestingly, most of the students consider mathematics as an important subject which has relevance in their daily life. This idea needs to be sustained among students learning mathematics.

Baloglu (2001), found that one of the reason for mathematical fear is attitude towards the subject, also found that when students failed constantly in mathematics, the anxiety can make he/she believe that he/she can never do well on the subject which will lead to failure and defeat or unsuccessful. In line with this Peker & Mirasyedioglu (2008), found that one of the factors of student's attitude towards mathematics teaching and learning is their mathematical attitude of fears, this hinders their success in learning mathematics and achievement. If fear is dealt with, it will yield a better and positive attitude toward teaching and learning. Also, Attard (2012), identified important factors that contribute to students' attitudes towards learning mathematics, these include the students themselves, the school, the teachers' beliefs and attitudes and their teaching methods. The findings show that attitude has very serious implications for the learner, the teacher, the immediate social group with which the individual learner relates, and the entire school system and it resulted to some kind of learning experiences students go through.

Nardi & Steward (2023), in the review of school-based educational research has revealed that the majority of secondary school students find mathematics as the most difficult, abstract, tedious, deadly, and boring subject. As such, Hançer, et al. (2017), found that students' attitudes towards mathematics changes according to some variables such as gender, whether receives private tuition, mathematics achievement score, educational background of parents, profession of parents and grade levels etc. it is required to understand students' attitude because one of the objectives of elementary mathematics education is to get student improve affirmative attitudes towards mathematics (Hançer, et al. 2017).

Afari et al., (2013) investigated the impact of using mathematical games on college students' attitudes towards learning Mathematics. A pre-post design method was used to assess students' perception of the learning environment and their attitude towards learning mathematics. The students from the classes that used games found their lessons more interactive, got involved and enjoyed learning mathematics. In line with this, Boaler (2016), when students are motivated by their teachers their mindsets, self confidence and hard work developed skill and ability in mathematics and will provide students with a strong understanding of what mathematics is. Thus, learners who develop a growth mindset, self confidence, believing that they can develop their intellectual ability through perseverance and effort, have positive attitudes and ongoing growth in mathematical achievement. Belief is crucial in learning mathematics because it required self confidence and mindset which will lead to positive attitude in learning of mathematics. However, Boaler (2016), stated that leaders should ask themselves positively and their teachers, parents and students about their beliefs concerning: what is mathematics and how is it best taught and learnt, and is one's mathematics ability fixed and immutable or can it be developed? Any positive response from teachers, parents and students will also develop a positive mindset to teaching and learning of mathematics.

Students' belief system is the powerful instrument that can change their attitude toward learning mathematics. If teachers' attitude and method of teaching mathematics are positive it has a powerful influence on student's belief and attitude formation toward mathematics. Students' positive attitude towards mathematics leads to better performance and may influence their overall achievement and application of mathematics in real-life. Success in learning mathematics depends on belief students have and positive attitude towards mathematics. It also influences the participation rate of learners (Dantani, 2023).

Conclusion

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This study has identified students' profiles of belief and attitude toward mathematics teaching and learning. It is concluded that students can have different attitudes toward mathematics, and they might need different kinds of support according to the individual components of their attitude toward mathematics. Therefore, teachers need to examine their students' attitude and provide appropriate support to stimulate the development of a positive attitude toward the subject. Furthermore, researchers should conduct additional studies to identify the factors leading to the development of students' negative attitude toward mathematics and offer suggestion on how students can be helped to develop a positive attitude.

Recommendations

The study recommends that:

1. Teachers should appropriately adopt instructional techniques that include learners' diversities or barriers to learning, minimize fear, enhance active interest, and enjoyment in what is being taught and learnt.
2. Teachers should prepare interesting mathematical tasks to engage their students in mathematics lessons that will enable them to enjoy mathematics. They should adjust the difficulties of mathematical tasks by considering their students' mathematical performance to ensure all students experience success in the mathematics classroom.
3. Mathematics teachers should develop positive attitude towards the subject and make mathematics interesting and appealing to students in order to help them develop a positive attitude towards it without any inhibition and improve their performance.
4. Students should use their time wisely so that they can have enough time to practice and internalise mathematical concepts learned in classrooms. This may help them acquire competencies, and thus improve their mathematics performance.
5. Student should monitor and reflect on the processes of mathematical problem solving. This will help them improve in learning the subject.
6. Government should provide teaching and learning resources. These should include enough qualified teachers, books, teaching and learning resources, and other instructional materials for effective learning of mathematics.
7. School administrators should provide teachers with educational resources (e.g., technological devices) and professional development programs to help them implement various instructional strategies in the mathematics classroom that would allow students to learn about the subject in an enjoyable manner.
8. Parents and teachers could provide accurate feedback and support to help students acquire accurate mathematical knowledge and develop confidence in mathematics. They should help students acquire awareness of the value of mathematics in their present and future life.

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